
Towards the development and applications of blood-brain barrier in vitro models for neurotoxicity assessment

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Abstract

To perform risk assessment of chemicals, drugs and particles, the regulatory OECD guidelines to determine neurotoxicity are based on animal testing. In addition to ethical concerns, inherent problems such as lack of translatability between animals and humans encouraged the development of new approach methodologies (NAMs) such as *in silico* and *in vitro* models. The development and validation of robust NAMs fit for regulatory needs are in line and support the current European policy of phasing out animal testing for which the European Commission will publish the roadmap in Q1/2026. The OECD has identified the role of the blood-brain barrier as a gap in the developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) test batteries currently being developed. As part of the European Partnership Programme PARC with over 200 participating research institutions, we developed different set-ups for adult neurotoxicity (ANT) and DNT testing based either on human iPSC-derived brain capillary endothelial-like cells (BCECs) or the immortalized cell line hCMEC/D3. The development of the BBB in vitro models, their applications and findings will be presented.

A set of selected neurotoxins, a mixture of PFAS and various nanoplastics were tested and showcased the broad applicability of the models obtaining data in one test set-up about permeability, changes of the barrier properties, the communication of the BBB with various CNS cells and effects on CNS cells on functional and molecular levels (e.g. RNAseq, DNA-methylation). One out of several interesting findings was the relevance of medium pH indicator phenolred for the successful BCECs differentiation revealed during studies about endocrine disruptors.

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